

Selection of suitable carbon and nitrogen sources on growth and production of L-glutamic acid by a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀

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Abstract : The production of L-glutamic acid with free cells of a mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was carried out using shake flask method through selection of suitable carbon and nitrogen sources. Among 12 different carbon sources and 10 nitrogen sources tested, 9.0% glucose and 1.4% diammonium hydrogen phosphate were selected as most suitable carbon and nitrogen sources respectively for the maximum growth and L-glutamic acid production by this mutant. Production increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 10.4 to 14.8 mg/ml. Dry cell weight also increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 4.6 to 7.3 mg/ml.

Keywords : L-Glutamic acid, mutant, *Micrococcus glutamicus*, carbon, nitrogen.

Introduction

Monosodium L-glutamate (MSG), the largest sodium salt among all amino acids is widely used now a day as flavor enhancer, feed supplements and therapeutics¹. Its annual demands exceeds 250 million pounds, bulk of which is produced by fermentation using *Micrococcus glutamicus* and *Brevibacterium* sp, mainly in USA and Japan². However, nutritional parameters namely carbon and nitrogen sources are known to significantly influence the product yield^{3,4}. Each microorganism has defined range of fermentation conditions and thus it is essential to investigate the influence of different carbon and nitrogen sources as nutritional parameters on L-glutamic acid production.

Various investigators used different carbon and nitrogen sources for microbial production of L-glutamic acid^{1,5-10}.

In our previous investigations we had already developed a high L-glutamic acid yielding strain of *Micrococcus glutamicus* by induced mutation and optimized different physical conditions to improve the fermentation^{11,12}. The present study was intended to select suitable carbon and nitrogen sources to further scale up this process.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism : A biotin-auxotrophic mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ developed in our laboratory from a regulatory mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁ by in-

duced mutation, was used for this study¹¹.

Composition of basal salt medium : Basal salt medium contained : glucose, 10.0%; urea, 0.8%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.025%; biotin, 0.2 µg/ml and pH was adjusted to 6.5 using 1(N) HCl and 1(N) NaOH¹³.

Analysis of amino acids : Descending paper chromatography was employed for the detection of L-glutamic acid in the production medium and was run for 16–18 h on a Whatman no. 1 chromatographic paper. Solvent system used contained : *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (2 : 1 : 1). The spot were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrin in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-glutamic acid was done using colorimetric procedure^{14,15}.

Estimation of dry cell weight (DCW) : After centrifugation, a few ml of 1(N) HCl was poured into the precipitate of the bacterial cells of calcium carbonate to dissolve calcium carbonate. The remaining cells were washed with water and dried at 10.0 °C until the cell weight remain constant¹⁶.

Statistical analysis : All data were expressed as mean ± SEM, where $n = 6$. The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post-hoc multiple comparison test using "prism 4.0" software (Graph pad Ind., USA). A "p" value less than 0.05 was considered significant and less than 0.01 as a highly significant.

Results and discussion

The influence of sucrose, lactose, maltose, arabinose, xylose, starch, galactose, sodium citrate, sodium acetate, glycerol and mannose on growth and production of L-glutamic acid was compared with that of glucose. Glucose in the basal salt medium was replaced by equivalent concentration of these carbon sources. Among them, glucose was proved to be the best for L-glutamic acid production by this mutant (Fig. 1). To optimize glucose concentration, varying concentrations of glucose (7.0–13.0%) were examined. Maximum production was obtained with 9.0% glucose (Fig. 2). Dry cell weight also showed similar pattern of changes.

In order to examine the influence of sodium nitrate, ammonium chloride, ammonium nitrate, diammonium hydrogen phosphate, ammonium oxalate, ammonium sulfate and ammonium citrate on growth and L-glutamic acid fermentation, urea of basal salt medium was replaced by equimolar concentration of various nitrogen sources. Diammonium hydrogen phosphate was proved to be the best nitrogen source for this mutant (Fig. 3). Among different concentrations of diammonium hydrogen phosphate (0.5–1.5%) studied, cellular growth and L-glutamic acid production were observed to be a function of nitrogen concentration upto 1.4% beyond which both cellular growth and the production were decreased (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Selection of suitable carbon source for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ (Values are expressed as mean ±SEM; where n=6; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 when compared to control).

Fig. 2. Selection of suitable glucose % for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ (Values are expressed as mean ±SEM; where n=6; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 when compared to control).

Fig. 3. Selection of suitable nitrogen sources for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ (Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM; where $n=6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 4. Optimization of diammonium hydrogen phosphate (%N) for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ (Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM; where $n=6$; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Takahashi *et al.*⁵ used 0.5% ammonium nitrate as nitrogen source for the production of L-glutamic acid by *Corynebacterium* sp. Cartio *et al.*¹⁷ studied the production of alanine by *Fusarium moniliforme* and reported that the production was maximum with 50 g glucose and 10.7 g urea in 50 ml fermentation broth¹⁷. 0.1% Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate and 0.1% diammonium hydrogen phosphate (as nitrogen source). 0.1% Urea, 0.1% ammonium dihydrogen phosphate and 0.1% diammonium hydrogen phosphate mixture (as nitrogen source) and 1% glucose as carbon source were used by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* for L-glutamic acid production¹⁸. Kato *et al.*¹⁹ obtained maximum L-proline by *Kurthia cateniforma* us-

ing 0.3% ammonium chloride and 0.5% urea mixture as nitrogen source and 6.0% glucose as carbon source. Yameda *et al.*²⁰ used 0.1% ammonium sulfate and 0.2% glucose for the production of L-glutamine by *Flavobacterium rigense*. Roy and Chatterjee⁶ reported that *Arthrobacter globiformis* accumulated L-glutamic acid in the fermentation broth with 8% glucose and 0.53% ammonium nitrate. Nompoothiri and Pandey²¹ studied the effect of different carbon source on growth and L-glutamic acid production by *Brevibacterium* sp and reported maximum production with 2.0% glucose medium. *Brevibacterium* sp accumulated maximum L-glutamic acid

in solid state fermentation using 2.0% glucose and 1.0% urea²². Sunitha *et al.*¹⁶ reported coimmobilized whole cells of *Pseudomonas replivora* and *Micrococcus glutamicus* in calcium alginate gel with 5.0% glucose and 0.8% L-glutamic acid production²³. *Corynebacterium glutamicum* was obtained with 2.0% glucose and 2.5% ammonium sulfate²⁴. Shah *et al.*¹⁶ optimized L-lysine production by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* with 10% glucose and 2.5% ammonium sulfate. Choi *et al.*⁷ obtained maximum L-glutamic acid with 12.0% glucose and 16.8% ammonia water. Ammonium nitrate (1.0%) was proved to be the best nitrogen source for L-glutamic acid production by *Brevibacterium divaricatum* MTCC 1529². Elwealor and Obeta²⁵ optimized L-lysine production by *Bacillus megaterium* with 8.0% glucose and 4.0% ammonium sulfate. Yugandhar *et al.*¹ optimized L-glutamic acid production by *Brevibacterium roseum* NCIM 2270 with 8.0% glucose and 0.8% urea. Threonine production by *E. coli* MT 201 required 5.0% glucose and 1.0% ammonium sulfate²⁶. Ekwealor and Obeta^{27,28} obtained maximum L-lysine by *Bacillus megaterium* sp 86 with 80.0 g sucrose and 80.0 g ammonium chloride; by *Bacillus megaterium* sp 76 and *Bacillus megaterium* sp 14 with 80.0 g glucose and 40.0 g ammonium sulfate^{27,28}. Yugandhar *et al.*⁹ obtained L-glutamic acid by free and immobilized cells of *Brevibacterium roseum* with 0.5% glucose and 0.5% urea. Patil *et al.*¹⁰ also used glucose and ammonium sulfate for the production of L-glutamic acid by whole and immobilized cells of *Corynebacterium glutamicum*¹⁰.

Pham *et al.*²⁹ claimed that excess carbon or nitrogen in the fermentation broth exerts osmotic pressure which might adversely affect the organism's growth and production of L-amino acids¹⁰. Production of L-glutamic acid by the free cells of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ was decreased above 9.0% glucose and 1.5% diammonium hydrogen phosphate, probably due to this reason. Thus, from this present study, it was clear that the production of L-glutamic acid was significantly ($p < 0.01$) increased from 10.4 to 14.8 mg/ml; dry cell weight increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 4.6 to 7.3 mg/ml after selection of suitable carbon and nitrogen sources.

Thus, from our present study we can tentatively conclude that maximum production of L-glutamic acid can

be obtained by the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₁₀₀ with 9.0% glucose and 1.4% diammonium hydrogen phosphate.

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